

**ATTITUDE TOWARDS COMPUTER USE AND MOTIVATION IN LEARNING
PHYSICAL EDUCATION AMONG JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS:
BASIS FOR A DEVELOPMENT PLAN**

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Attitude Towards Computer Use and Motivation in Learning Physical Education among Junior High School Students: Basis for a Development Plan

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Abstract

This study determined the influence of attitude towards computer use and motivation in learning physical education among junior high school students. Stratified random sampling was used in choosing the schools and simple random sampling in choosing respondents from secondary schools of Lupon West District. Validated and reliability tested survey questionnaires were used to gather data. Mean, standard deviation, Pearson Product Moment Correlation, and linear regression were among the statistical tools used. The results revealed that students had a high level of attitude towards computer use and motivation in learning physical education. Likewise, there was a significant relationship between attitude towards computer use and motivation in learning physical education among junior high school students. Moreover, perceived usefulness and behavioral intention of attitude towards computer significantly influence motivation in learning physical education. However, the other indicators of attitude towards computer use namely affective component and perceived control were not predictors of students motivation in learning physical education. Based on the findings, proposed development plan was made.

Keywords: *education, physical education, attitude towards computer use, motivation, descriptive correlation*

Introduction

Motivation has an important influence on a learner's attitude especially in learning physical education. According to a survey, because of online learning 55 percent of students felt less motivated to learn due to concerns in lack of social interaction, and the same concern is true in teaching physical education online. The abrupt shift to virtual instruction led to worse outcomes for students (Department of Education, 2021). Students may have challenging learning opportunities or learning may be less than optimal, especially in courses that require face-to-face contact and direct interactions like physical education (Little, 2019; Franchi, 2020).

Issues concerning lack of motivation in learning especially subjects that requires face-to-face interaction like physical education where varied. In the US, Pinto (2022) emphasized depersonalization. Wherein depersonalization includes reasons by students in Minnesota, like not wanting to turn on their cameras or microphones, and others did not log on to participate in the class during PE online class session (Benecke, 2021). Likewise, in Seoul, South Korea, Yu and Jee (2021), and Jeong and So (2020) pointed the poorly designed online lecture that causes learners to become lost, lose interest, feel distressed, and the limited feedback from teachers resulted to students not able to modify their own physical activities.

Moreover, Shen et al. (2022) found that lack of motivation in learning physical education may result from different reasons. Moreover, in Carnegie Mellon University (2022) provided reasons like students may suffer from physical, mental, or other personal problems that affect motivation. More so, students may have other priorities that compete for their time and attention and do not believe that their efforts will improve their performance in learning physical education.

Moreover, in the Philippines, some students are not motivated because they may have a wrong opinion of physical education because they do not like how the instructor runs the class or the activity itself (Cruz et al., 2021). On the other hand, in Surigao del Sur, Balacuit and Inabangan (2019) stated that some elementary, secondary, and even tertiary public and private school teachers have expressed dissatisfaction with students' lack of enthusiasm for games and sports, except for those with a high degree of bodily-kinesthetic intelligence because of several demanding activities and other factors, these pupils take the subject for granted. Likewise, in Davao Del Sur, students had problems gaining motivation in learning because they were afraid of mistakes and are also less motivated due to the lack of creative setup in the classroom (Corsino et al., 2022).

Moreover, according to Gallagher (2020) if students have positive attitude towards computer use, employing the use of computers in physical education might motivate and entice students to participate in physical education. He went on to say that using computers in physical education will boost student-teacher connection. In the same way, employing the right computers in physical education can encourage learners, involve them in what they are learning, and help them grasp it better. Similarly, computers boosts creativity because it is an interactive medium that allows students to participate in meaningful creative activities and discover their potential (Thangarajathi, 2020).

Moreover, the application of computer might be helpful for learners in improving their reading, writing, listening, speaking, and performing skills, as well as encouraging autonomy in learning (Beatty, 2018). In general, technology has improved physical education lessons. Students' positive attitude in the use of computers made physical education lessons enjoyable, pleasant, and satisfying since instructors can set individualized and practical goals for their pupils using applications, and online videos (McVicker, 2022).

The studies of Furrion (2019), Kuan (2020), and Angh (2020) only focus on the influence of computers on learning motivation among

students without delving into the effects of computer attitude among learners. Deshmukh (2020) also focuses on the digital competence and skills needed in the pandemic. Meanwhile, this study's researcher focuses only on the attitude towards computer use and motivation in learning physical education among junior high school students and the creation of the development plan based on the findings of the study made this study have more added social value. Also, examination of the attitude towards computer use and motivation in learning of the students may provide teachers and policymakers a more balanced perspective, one that considers not only the possible adverse effects but also the benefits of engaging in attitude towards computer use.

The researcher is eager to disseminate the research findings engagingly and innovatively to the direct beneficiaries of the study through research forums organized by the Department of Education and other research organizations. If there is an opportunity, this study will be published in an appropriate avenue for more excellent distribution in highly trusted academic journals.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the relationship between attitude towards computer use and motivation in learning physical education among junior high school students. Specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of attitude towards computer use in terms of:
 - 1.1. affective component;
 - 1.2. perceived usefulness;
 - 1.3. perceived control; and
 - 1.4. behavioral intention?
2. What is the level of motivation in learning physical education in terms of:
 - 2.1. self-efficacy;
 - 2.2. intrinsic value;
 - 2.3. cognitive strategy use; and
 - 2.4. self-regulation?
3. Is there a significant relationship between attitude towards computer use and motivation in learning physical education of the junior high school students?
4. Which of the indicators of attitude towards computer use significantly influence the level of motivation in learning physical education of the junior high school students?
5. Based on the result, what development plan can be formulated?

Literature Review

Attitude towards Computer Use and Motivation in Learning Physical Education

The authors found that students were more likely to engage in an activity simply because computer is being used. However, almost 50 of surveyed teachers used computer for 80 or fewer minutes per day. After implementing a technological intervention, students stated that they felt teachers provided activities relevant to them, and motivation and engagement went up 9 percent for all students (Godzicki et al., 2016).

Also, the students believe computers will enable them to learn more effectively and autonomously. They think they can learn more quickly and creatively with computers. They believe they have more influence over their education and practice chances.

Moreover, students have more flexible studying opportunities thanks to online resources. Some students may use a YouTube video tutorial to comprehend a concept fully. Others might play a game or complete an online task that offers immediate feedback to determine if they're on the right course (NextThought Studio, 2020).

In summary, computers has improved physical education lessons, providing new opportunities for applying an audio-visual approach, cognitive approach, and communicative approach. Likewise, motivation has an important influence on a learner's attitude and learning behavior, and academic motivation is a key determinant of academic performance. Moreover, motivated learners display a number of behaviors that allow them to perform according to their academic abilities.

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a non-experimental design utilizing the descriptive correlation technique of research which is designed to gather data, ideas, facts and information related to the study. According to Myers and Well (2013) correlated design examines how the independent variable influences the dependent variable and establishes cause and effect relationship between variables. It enabled the researcher to observe two variables at a point in time and was useful in describing the relationship of the factors of both variables. Through statistical analysis, the relationship will be given a degree and a direction.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 201 junior high school students in the three schools in Lupon, Davao Oriental, Philippines. The researcher used Raosoft Calculator to determine the exact number of respondents, 201 junior high school students. In using a Raosoft Calculator, the researcher used 5 percent as the margin error, 90 percent as the confidence level, 50 percent as the response distribution, and 766 as the population size resulting to 201 recommended sample size. The researcher used stratified random sampling to obtain a sample population that best represents the entire population being studied, making sure that each subgroup of interest is represented. Also, simple random sampling method was utilized to selecting the respondents per school.

Moreover, the respondents of the study have the following inclusion criteria: were bonafide students from the Department of Education in Lupon West District, Davao Oriental and were enrolled in physical education subjects in Grade 10 in School A, School B, or School C in Lupon West District, Davao Oriental. On the contrary, elementary students, senior high school students, SPED students, teachers, and parents were not part of this study.

Instruments

The study employed the questionnaires adapted from different studies and was modified to fit the context of the respondents of this study. The first part is about attitude towards computer use adopted from the Computer Attitude Scale (CAS) survey questionnaire of Saricoban (2013) indicated with affective component, perceived usefulness, perceived control, and behavioural intention. The instrument is composed of 21 statements and uses a five point Likert scale having Cronbach's Alpha of 0.70.

The second part of the instrument is about the motivation in learning physical education of the junior high school students. The questionnaire is adapted from the study of Kubischta (2014). Motivation for learning physical education (PE) is measured in terms of self-efficacy, intrinsic value, cognitive strategy use, and self-regulation. The instrument is composed of 40 statements and uses a five point Likert scale: 5-Strongly Agree, 4-Agree, 3-Fairly Agree, 2-Disagree, 1-Strongly Disagree. The instrument was tested for internal consistency and obtain an overall Cronbach's alpha value of 0.783.

Procedure

The researcher took the following steps in the gathering of data. First, the researcher asked permission from the Dean of the Graduate School of the University of the Immaculate Conception. The researcher also secured an Ethical Clearance from the University of Immaculate Conception Research Ethics Committee (UIC-REC). Upon approval, the researcher wrote a letter to the Superintendent of Davao Oriental Division asking to conduct the study in Lupon District. Once the request was granted, the researcher sent a communication to the school heads indicating the intention to conduct the survey in the district. The researcher then attached the letter of approval from the division superintendent. Considering the new typical setup amidst the upsurge of COVID-19, the researcher followed proper health protocols. All letters of consent and Informed Consent Form (ICF) were sent and retrieved through online platforms. The survey forms were given to the junior high school students using Google forms to follow the IATF (Inter-Agency Tasks Force) health protocols. The interpretation of the data followed after the statistician handed the data.

Ethical Considerations

The ethical procedure was observed in the conduct of this study. This was done to avoid any harm or malicious acts that the respondents would experience. The University of the Immaculate Conception Research Ethics Committee (UIC-REC) evaluated the paper to review whether the study adhered to the university's ethical standards. The ethical principles are discussed below.

Social Value. In this study, the respondents, who are junior high school students, are adequately informed of the purpose of the research and make them understand the study's goals, which is to address existing research gaps in attitude toward computer use and motivation in learning physical education of junior high school students. They were given photocopied materials of the questionnaires to measure attitude towards computer use and motivation in learning. Furthermore, the research will be shared the results and findings of the study with proper authorities in the Division of Davao Oriental. These authorities may include the Division Research Committee Chair, the Lupon West District through the research focal person, the school heads of each school, and the physical education students in the junior high schools in Lupon West District.

Informed Consent. The researcher used an Informed Consent Form or ICF, an essential document in the conduct of the study. To secure this, the researcher informed the respondents about the objectives and benefits of the study. The researcher himself included disclosing the essential information about the research and the data about the researcher to establish rapport, trust, and confidence among the respondents. He explained that the researcher is currently studying the attitude towards computer use and motivation in learning physical education and its significant relationship. Further, the respondents also given thorough explanations of their participation in the study. The study results can also help them improve their attitude towards computer use and motivation in learning physical education.

Vulnerability of the Research Participants. Most respondents of this study were below 18 years old, and they were considered vulnerable as they are not of legal age enough to decide for themselves to participate in the study. The researcher utilized the Research Ethics Assent Form to be distributed to the parents of children ages 18 and below. However, some of the respondents of this study were not

be considered vulnerable by the researcher since they can opt out when they feel weak or emotionally affected by the contents of this study. They voluntarily and directly gave their consent to be involved in the data collection upon recruitment. The information that have been collected in this research will be used solely to gather findings about the research problem. Information that have been gathered in this study was not be used for other purposes. Furthermore, the junior high school students agreed with the study's nature. The researcher established rapport and confidence to make the respondents feel at ease and safer and more protected.

Risks, Benefits, and Safety. This study was not expected to have a high risk since it was conducted through online platforms, explicitly using Google Form during their break time. The respondents also gain benefits in participating in the research. One of which was that they were informed of their attitude towards computer use and motivation in learning physical education. Moreover, they also get the chance to understand the different indicators consisting of these variables.

Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. The researcher informed the respondents about the practice to observe the value of confidentiality. In adherence to the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the researcher made sure to keep the recorded information in the data gathering procedure safe, secure, and not made accessible to anybody. There were no names written in the questionnaire. To truly uphold privacy and secrecy in the process, the researcher did not disclose to anybody the survey tool which the respondents have answered. Similarly, the researcher prohibited sharing information about the respondents to ensure anonymity. Likewise, there were no information to be shared attributed to the respondents to ensure secrecy. Since data collection was done online, all recorded responses were kept confidential with security pins and passwords and only that the researcher can access. To observe the requirements of the Data Privacy Act of the Philippines, the researcher distributed the Informed Consent Form online to the respondents. By signing and returning this consent form to the researcher, the respondents confirmed and allowed the researcher to collect, use, record, store, organize and consolidate personal data. The respondents' permission to be granted to the researcher was responsibly handled and respected.

Justice. The researcher employed appropriate sampling technique to avoid bias in this study. Respondents were made aware of their responsibility to answer the questionnaire honestly and truthfully. Consequently, the researcher also assured them that their participation were be treated with importance and priority since the results and findings may benefit them in the future. Furthermore, the researcher gave tokens of appreciation to the respondents who were generous in sharing their time and effort as respondents of this study.

Transparency. In analyzing the data, the researcher conveyed the study's outcome fully and accurately. Since the study is quantitative, the data were presented and reflected exactly from the statistical test result. The researcher also acknowledged the effort of every person who contributed to the study's success. The Division of Davao Oriental and Lupon West District will be given a copy of the research results. It may be used for learning and further study. Moreover, the researcher will publish the research findings in journals so that a large number of people can read the study's outcome. Furthermore, the researcher also discussed the risks and benefits of this study to guide them in their investigation correctly.

Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher was qualified since he was exposed to research as a Master of Arts in Education student. The researcher sought the expertise of his research adviser, a qualified expert determined by the institution, to guide and help the researcher fulfill the study at hand throughout the entire study duration. The research adviser is a Doctor of Philosophy in Organization Study graduate with many research publications. The research adviser was willing and eager to assist the researcher in fulfilling the study. At the same time, feedback from the technical and ethical examining committee and the research director also served as guiding factors to finishing this research successfully. The said professionals' guidance enabled the researcher to gather the needed data for the research.

Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher ensures adequate and available resources are needed in this study. Books, online journals, and unpublished thesis or dissertations were available to provide references for several literature and studies supporting the study variables' relationship. Internet connection and gadgets necessary for the study fulfillment are made available by the researcher. These include mobile phones, computers, laptops, and desktops noted during the entire research process.

Community Involvement. Before conducting the study, the researcher informed the involved schools and their school heads. The researcher wrote a letter to the respective leaders of the schools to seek necessary permission. The consent included the extent of time, the potential impact and outcomes of the research, and who is involved. Once approved, the researcher will conduct a symposium to discuss the result of the study and significance of the study with the parents, teachers, and school administrators of the Lupon West District

Results and Discussion

Attitude Towards Computer Use of Junior High School Students

Shown in Table 1 is the result of the attitude toward computer use of junior high school students.

Table 1. Attitude Towards Computer Use

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
Affective Component			
1. Being not afraid to use a computer.	4.15	0.82	High
2. Not hesitating to use a computer.	2.85	1.06	Moderate
3. Not feeling apprehensive about using a computer.	3.19	1.01	Moderate
4. Being comfortable with using computers.	3.47	1.18	High
5. Not being scared in using a computer.	3.83	0.98	High
6. Not hesitating to use a computer despite of the possibility of damage.	2.76	1.12	Moderate
Category Mean	3.49	0.61	High
Perceived Usefulness			
1. Computers helping them to improve their work better.	4.47	0.73	Very High
2. Computers making it possible for them to work more productively.	4.26	0.79	Very High
3. Computers allowing them to do more interesting and imaginative work.	4.27	0.81	Very High
4. Being able to use computers to do most of the things at work.	3.93	0.86	High
5. Computers enhancing the presentation of their work.	4.27	0.80	Very High
Category Mean	4.25	0.65	Very High
Perceived Control			
1. Teaching themselves most of the things they need to know about computers.	4.06	0.88	High
2. Making the computer do what they want to.	3.52	0.95	High
3. Knowing how to solve computer problems one way or another.	3.31	1.02	Moderate
4. Controlling completely when they use computers.	3.51	0.97	High
5. Using computer on their own.	3.94	0.91	High
6. Using the computer without someone telling them how.	3.29	1.22	Moderate
Category Mean	3.68	0.69	High
Behavioral Intention			
1. Doing a job involving computers.	3.23	1.30	Moderate
2. Not avoiding using with computers at school.	3.24	1.17	Moderate
3. Using computers at school when they are told to.	3.86	1.09	High
4. Using computers regularly throughout school.	3.11	1.07	Moderate
Category Mean	3.48	0.66	Moderate
Total Mean	3.64	0.52	High

Motivation in Learning Physical Education of Junior High School Students

Table 2 shows the status of motivation in learning physical education of junior high school students.

Table 2. Motivation in Learning Physical Education

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
Self-efficacy			
1. Doing well in physical activities.	3.80	0.96	High
2. Understanding ideas related to physical education.	4.05	0.74	High
3. Doing well in physical education.	3.99	0.83	High
4. Being a good student.	4.19	0.92	High
5. Doing an excellent performance on performing physical activities and tasks given in physical education class.	3.87	0.84	High
6. Receiving a good grade for being physically active.	3.95	0.89	High
7. Having excellent study skills.	3.63	0.95	High
8. Being knowledgeable about physical education.	3.63	0.87	High
9. Learning from doing physical activities in class.	4.11	0.81	High
Category Mean	3.92	0.65	High
Intrinsic Value			
1. Choosing a challenging physical activities.	4.14	0.85	High
2. Learning from the physical activities introduced by the teachers.	4.28	0.79	Very High
3. Liking what they learn in doing physical activities.	4.16	0.84	High
4. Using what they learn in doing physical activities.	4.14	0.82	High
5. Choosing moderate to vigorous activities to acquire more skills.	3.82	0.91	High
6. Learning from their mistakes.	4.40	0.70	Very High
7. Learning physical education is helpful to them.	4.35	0.83	Very High
8. Learning to do physical activities is interesting.	4.34	0.83	Very High
9. Understanding physical education is important to them.	4.35	0.86	Very High
Category Mean	4.27	0.65	Very High
Cognitive Strategy Use			
1. Trying to put together information from the video presentations presented by the teacher during discussions and from other resources.	4.19	0.83	High

2. Trying to remember what the other group-members have told them.	4.00	0.76	High
3. Deciding the main ideas when they perform.	2.23	0.83	Low
4. Recalling the important details to perform better.	4.12	0.81	High
5. Trying to understand what the others are saying even if it doesn't make any sense.	3.86	0.86	High
6. In preparing for the performance task, trying to remember as many facts as they can.	4.13	0.80	High
7. Watching video instructional materials to help them remember the skills needed to perform.	4.12	0.87	High
8. In preparing for a presentation, practicing the important skills over and over.	4.10	0.86	High
9. Learning from the previous discussions and video materials to do the tasks given.	4.07	0.78	High
10. Trying to make everything fit together.	4.01	0.70	High
11. Imagining the video materials for the performance to help them remember.	4.16	0.77	High
12. Re-watching the video materials and reading the textbooks during their free time to help them remember the important details to accomplish the task given.	4.03	0.85	High
13. Trying to reminisce the things they practiced about with what they already know to perform the task given appropriately.	4.01	0.85	High
Category Mean	3.91	0.51	High
Self-regulation			
1. Asking themselves questions to make sure they know the skills when performing.	4.22	0.80	Very High
2. Never giving up or execute the easy parts when physical activity is hard.	2.36	0.98	Low
3. Working on practice exercises and preparing extra material even when they don't have to.	3.76	0.85	High
4. Keep working until they finish even when the materials for the performance task are dull and uninteresting	3.88	0.86	High
5. Thinking about the things they will need to do to learn before performing the task given.	4.13	0.76	High
6. Thinking of other things on how to make them perform better.	4.09	0.91	High
7. Stopping once in a while to think if they are doing it right and go over what they have performed.	4.09	0.89	High
8. Working hard to get a good grade even when they don't like the activities.	4.15	0.97	High
Category Mean	3.93	0.55	High
Total Mean	3.95	0.52	High

Significance of the Relationship Between Attitude Towards Computer Use and Motivation in Learning Physical Education

As shown in table 3, the correlation between attitude towards computer use and motivation in learning physical education shows significant relationship since the p-value is less than .05, wherein the result is $p=.001$.

Table 3. *Significance of the Relationship Between Attitude Towards Computer Use and Motivation in Learning Physical Education*

<i>Attitude Towards Computer Use</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>p value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Motivation in Learning Physical Education	0.268	.001	Significant

Significant Influence of the Indicators of Attitude Towards Computer Use to Motivation in Learning Physical Education

Table 4 shows the significant influence of attitude towards computer use to motivation in learning physical education.

Table 4. *Significant Influence of Attitude Towards Computer Use to Motivation in Learning Physical Education*

<i>Motivation in Learning Physical Education</i>	<i>Standardized Beta Coefficients</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Affective Component	-.044	-.618	.537	Not Significant
Perceived Usefulness	.352	5.142	.000	Significant
Perceived Control	.075	1.110	.269	Not Significant
Behavioral Intention	.161	2.337	.020	Significant
Combined Influence of Predictors				
R	.417			
R ²	0.174			
F	10.302			
Sig.	.000			Significant

Proposed Development Plan

I. Rationale

This proposed development plan will improve students attitude towards computer use and motivation in learning physical education. Students need to be comfortable and familiar with using computers to gather and distribute information. Motivation helps students focus their attention on a key goal, leading to goal-oriented behaviours, resilience, curiosity, and respect.

II. Objectives

To request additional budget to DepEd funds, Local funds, PTA funds, and other Stakeholders for additional computers, extension of computer laboratories, internet connection, and seminar/workshops;

To conduct orientation to students on how to use computers;

To organize and systematize participation in sports, culture, and arts competitions inside and outside the school; and

To establish linkages with schools and agencies involved in computer.

<i>Variables/ Indicators</i>	<i>Objectives</i>	<i>Program/ Activities/ Projects To Be Undertaken</i>	<i>Time Frame</i>	<i>Persons Responsible</i>	<i>Evaluation Measures/ Success Indicators</i>
Attitude towards Computer Use – Affective Component, Perceived Control, and Behavioral Intention	1. To request additional budget to DepEd funds, Local funds, PTA funds, and Other Stakeholders 2. To conduct orientation on how to use computers	1. Extend Computer Laboratories 2. Additional Computers 3. Provide high internet connection 3. Seminar/ Workshops	Year Round	1. Physical Education Teachers 2. School Admin 3. Deped	1. 50% additional MOOE funds for computer laboratories extension, additional computers, and high internet connection 2. 90% of the students attended seminars/ workshops on how to use computers
Motivation in learning physical education – Cognitive Strategy Use and Self-regulation Regression Result	1. To organize and systematize participation in sports, culture, and arts competitions inside and outside the school 1. To establish linkages with schools and agencies involved in computer.	1. Physical Education Day 2. School Intramurals 3. Sports, Culture, and Arts Clinic 1. Computer Systems Servicing NC II	Year Round	1. Physical Education Teachers 2. School Admin 3. DepEd 1. Physical Education Teachers 2. DepEd	1. 100% of the students attended sports, culture, and arts competitions inside and outside the school 1. 100% MOU signed by the school and agencies involved in computer 2. 100% of the students passed the Computer Systems Servicing NC II

Shown in Table 1 is the result of the attitude towards computer use of junior high school students. The overall mean rating is 3.64 described as high, which means that attitude towards computer use are oftentimes observed and with a standard deviation of 0.52, indicating that the respondents’ responses do not vary. This implies that students perceived the use computers important and computers make their studies better, more entertaining, and more creative. The result parallel to what Forcier (2016) said that using computer may help students to enhance the presentation of their works. This result also supports what Granng (2017) had emphasized where using computers can improve the learning process of the students like to create multimedia presentation that can improve their understanding, enthusiasm, class attendance and satisfaction. In addition, according to White (2016), using computers in the classroom can enhance student learning. Likewise, Butler and Mautz (2016) stated that students are more motivated and attend class more regularly when using computers at school.

Affective Component. The respondents evaluate the affective component of attitude towards computer use as high with a mean rating of 3.49 and the mean ranges from 2.76-4.15. Specifically, the statement being not afraid to use a computer with a mean of 4.15. Likewise, the item not hesitating to use a computer despite of the possibility of damage with a mean of 2.76. This implies that some of the students may do not have negative experience of using a computer. This result supports the study of McVicker (2022) where it revealed that since students are used to play applications like in online games they are not hesitant in using it. Also, the findings of this study aligns with the study of Beatty (2018) where it revealed that since students are confident in using computers they use it to improve their reading, writing, listening, speaking, and performing skills. Likewise, Truchot (2022) emphasized that the affective component concerns how a person internally feels, including whether that feeling is positive or negative, attractive, liked, or involves an evaluation and in this case the students are at ease with using computers. Additionally, Certy (2018) points out that using computer software as supplementary materials in the classroom opens up new chances for employing an audio-visual, cognitive, and communicative approach.

Perceived Usefulness. This category has obtained a very high rating of 4.25. In addition, the mean ranges from 3.93-4.47. Specifically, the item being able to use computers to do most of the things at work with a mean of 3.93. Also, the item having computers help them to improve their work better with a mean of 4.47. This implies that students are using computers to produce a good output on their tasks and minimize their work. This findings parallel to what Kenning and Kenning (2018) said which revealed that students are using computers to become responsible for their own learning that is using computers to complete their assignments. This findings also aligns with the study of Tahir et al. (2020) where computers can enhance students’ ability to accomplish their tasks to create more interesting and imaginative work. In addition, according to Graham (2018), perceived usefulness relates to user’s arbitrary beliefs that utilizing particular technologies can improve their capacity to complete tasks. Students take ownership of their education by identifying their learning preferences. In other words, given that students are allowed to study and learn independently, computers may play a big part in the process (Kenning & Kenning, 2018).

Perceived Control. The table shows the perceived control of attitude towards computer use which is high with a mean rating of 3.68. Moreover, the mean ranges from 3.29-4.06. Specially, the statement not needing someone to tell them how to use a computer with a mean 3.29. Additionally, the item being able to teach themselves most of the things they need to know about computers with a mean of 4.06. This implies that some students may need some supervision from someone on how to use computer. Also, some students are afraid of being mocked if they make mistakes in using computers that is why students try their best to learn the use of computer. The findings of this study affirms to what Taylor (2017) said where some students work on their own and at their own pace without needing someone to assist them in the use of computers. Thus, students are responsible for everything they do in using computers (Kenning & Kenning, 2018). More so, the results aligns with the study of Ly et al. (2022), where he found out that students has high perceived control. Thus, students allowing students to be responsible for everything they do (Tahar et al., 2020).

Behavioural Intention. The respondents evaluated the behavioral intention of attitude towards computer use as moderate with a mean rating of 3.48. The table further reveals that the mean ranges from 3.11-3.86. Looking closely at the result, the item using computers regularly throughout school has a mean rating of 3.11. Additionally, the item using computers at school when they are told to get the rating of 3.86. This implies that students are not allowed to use the computers anytime they want but instead depending on the subject where they are allowed to use. The findings support what Dunkel (2018) said where it reveals that schools recognize the use of computers as important for the success in the learning process of the students. This findings also aligns with the study of Graham (2018) wherein the opportunities given by school to the students in using computers allows students to develop positive feelings about the use of computers in instruction, thus, making the students likely to be more willing to learn and take the responsibility for their own learning. More so, according to LaMorte (2019), the motivational elements that affect a particular conduct are referred to as behavioral intention, and the stronger the intention to carry out the activity, the more probable it is that the behavior will be carried out. Since computer programs are considered tools that enhance autonomy in learning, students' attitudes towards computer instructions in classrooms are essential for success in the learning process (Dunkel, 2018). If the students have positive feelings about using computers in instruction, they will likely be more willing to learn and take responsibility for their learning.

Table 2 shows the status of motivation in learning physical education of junior high school students. It reveals that the total mean scores of the status of motivation in learning physical education is 3.95 described as high, which means that the motivation in learning physical education of the respondents is oftentimes evident. The domains self-efficacy, intrinsic value, cognitive strategy use, and self-regulation have category means of 3.92, 4.27, 3.91, and 3.93, respectively. Also, the overall standard deviation is 0.52 indicates that Junior High School students' responses do not vary among all items and indicators. This implies that students are motivated in learning physical education because they believed that learning physical education is helpful in their daily lives and doing physical activities is very interesting. The result parallels what Nur et al. (2022) said where he revealed that students who are motivated to learn are driven and willing to take action to accomplish physical activities and tasks offered in physical education class at a high level. The findings also confirm the report by Rabinowitz and Glaser (2018) where they emphasized that strategies help students have an excellent performance in physical education class. Likewise, Nur et al. (2022) stressed that motivation to learning is a psychological concept that guides individuals in reaching goals and considers the psychological assets utilized to support actions. Motivation has an influence on a learner's attitude and learning behavior (Hakan & Munire, 2018).

Self-efficacy. Self-efficacy with a mean of 3.92 described as high. The table further reveals that the mean ranges from 3.63-4.19. Looking closely at the result, the item having excellent study skills and being knowledgeable about physical education has a mean rating of 3.63. Additionally, the item being a good student got the rating of 4.19. This implies that students are doing well in physical education class and are knowledgeable about physical education. Subsequently, the result supports Hood (2022) where he revealed in his study that students are more participative in activities where they are interested thus, making them more knowledgeable. This result is also parallel to what Acola (2017) revealed that students give their best in doing their performance tasks in physical education class (Acola, 2017). In addition, students strive for excellence and efficacy when they are motivated (Ogunsola, 2019). Making the motivated learners to give their best in whatever they do and their school activities, like performing presentations and participating in class activities and discussions (Xiong et al., 2022).

Intrinsic Value. This type of motivation was also rated by Junior High School students very high, with a mean of 4.27 and the mean ranges from 3.82-4.40. Looking closely at the items, choosing moderate to vigorous activities to acquire more skills have a rating of 3.82. Also the item learning from their mistakes, which attained 4.40. This implies that students wanted to choose challenging activities in physical education class. These results are clearly in confirmation to Silvia (2016) where he exposed that students are naturally driven to do choose activities and learn from it if they appreciate their academic tasks. Also, the result is supports the study of Urbina (2017) where it reveals that students apply what they have learned when engaging in physical activity. More so, Kpolovie (2018) stated that interest in learning could be a powerful affective psychological trait, knowledge emotion, and a magnetic positive feeling that can help cognitively process information faster and more accurately. Likewise, the nature and strength of one's interest in learning and schooling may represent an essential aspect of personality (Urbina, 2017).

Cognitive Strategy Use. This type of motivation has a mean of 3.91 described as high, with a mean ranging from 2.23-4.19. Based on the results in Table 2, the item deciding the main ideas when they perform got a rating of 2.23. Similarly, the item that says trying to put together information from the video presentations presented by the teacher during discussions and from other resources with a mean rating of 4.19. This implies that students have difficulty fully grasping the main idea when they perform the physical activity, which

prevents them from completing the task at hand. This result supports what Moor (2020) said where it emphasized that the students need to grasp the key concept in order to accurately understand what they have just read and watched for them to be able to perform properly the physical activity. More so, the result aligns with Livingston (2020) where divulges that students are more driven to view video presentations to gather more knowledge. If students are interested in the material, they will remember and process it more successfully. Further, Silvia (2016) said that motivated students are profoundly engaged in their work, feel satisfied, and actively seek out obstacles with the goal of succeeding in them. Furthermore, Muni (2018) motivated learners display several behaviors that allow them to perform accordingly to their academic abilities. Adding on, motivated children become deeply involved in the task at hand and experience a feeling of enjoyment (Silvia, 2016), and they seek out challenges to conquer them (Muni, 2018).

Self-Regulation. Lastly, self-regulation gets a mean of 3.95 described as high. Based on the results shown in table 2, the mean ranges from 2.36-4.22. The item that says never giving up or execute the easy parts when physical activity is hard with the rating 2.36. Likewise, the item that says asking themselves questions to make sure they know the skills when performing with a mean rating of 4.22. This implies that before completing the task given, students consider what they will need to do to learn. Additionally, even when they dislike the activities, students put forth a lot of effort to achieve high grades. The result supports what McCormack (2022) noted where students have the mental capacity to understand and regulate their actions and responses thus, even if they do not like the activity since they need to pass they were able to eventually shift from displeasure to enthusiasm. Further, this result agrees with Wigfield (2018) that students know how to do self-evaluation, self-inspection, and self-control at various phases of their learning. Furthermore, Alexander and Harris (2018) said that self-regulated students can easily increase their understanding and memory in carrying out tasks. This scenario means that self-regulated learners have different cognitive strategies – like repetition, rehearsal, elaboration, and organization – which they can easily use for better comprehension and memory improvement in their school work (Alexander & Harris, 2018).

As shown in table 3, the correlation between attitude towards computer use and motivation in learning physical education shows significant relationship since the p-value is less than .05, wherein the result is $p=.001$. In this current study on attitude towards computer use, Junior High School students motivation in learning physical education do significantly related. The result somehow agrees with what Godzicki et al. (2016) said where they revealed that students are more likely to participate in a physical activity when computers are being used since they believe that computers will help them study more rapidly and creatively. The same perspective with Livingston (2020) where it emphasizes that using computers give students more flexible study options, like a video presentations to properly understand the idea, resulting to positive attitude thus, students are more motivated to do physical activity. In addition, Godzicki et al. (2016), said that students believe computers will enable them to learn more effectively and autonomously. Likewise, allowing them to learn more quickly and creatively with computers. With this positive attitude, students have more influence over their education and practice chances (Romero-Blanco et al., 2020).

Table 4 shows the significant influence of attitude towards computer use to motivation in learning physical education. The finding shows that the indicators of attitude towards compute use such as perceived usefulness and behavioral intention significantly influence students motivation in learning physical education as seen in the p-value, which is less than .05. Further, the result of the F ratio in Table 4 indicates that the overall regression model is a good fit in this study ($F=10.302$, $p<.05$). Furthermore, the table can only explain 17.4 percent of the students motivation in learning physical education as revealed in the R-squared value of 0.174. This suggests that 82.6 percent of the variance can be attributed to other factors aside from perceived usefulness and behavioral intention. More so, the other indicators of attitude towards computer use namely affective component and perceived control are not predictors of students motivation in learning physical education as seen in the p-value which is greater than 0.05.

The crafted development plan are based on the findings of this study. Some statements of the three indicators of attitude towards computer use namely affective component, perceived control, and behavioral intention got a mean rating ranges from 2.76-3.31 described as moderate. Some statements of the two indicators of motivation in learning physical education namely cognitive strategy use and self-regulation got a mean rating ranges from 2.23-2.36 described as low. Based on the result, the researcher formulated a development plan that will help the students to foster their learning and develop their skills in using computers.

Conclusions

The level of attitude towards computer use among junior high school students was high. This implies that students used computers to improve, entertain, and enhance their creative work. However, some students may still need assistance in using computers.

The level of motivation in learning physical education among junior high school students was high. This implies that students are motivated to acquire physical education because they think it will be engaging and beneficial to them in their daily lives. Through motivated strategies, students are performing well in physical education class.

There was a significant relationship between attitude towards computer use and motivation in learning physical education among Junior High School students. This implies that when computers are being used, students are more likely to participate in an activity. Students learn more effectively and independently with the use of computers. In order fully comprehend the key ideas of the task given, students used computers to watch video presentations.

Perceived usefulness and behavioral intention of attitude towards computer use significantly influence motivation of students in learning physical education. This implies that some students are using computers because they are well-equipped and skilled. Students can learn more quickly and creatively with the use of computers. Students are using computers to improve their work better and create imaginative works during physical education class.

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